

CRIMINAL CONSCIOUSNESS
IN
FYODOR DOSTOEVSKY'S
CRIME AND PUNISHMENT

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project work on criminal consciousness in Dostoevsky's Crime and Punishment was done by Omobuwajo Deborah Adeyinka of the Department of English, Faculty of Arts, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.

In partial fulfilment of the requirement of the award of Bachelor of Arts degree.
(Literature-in-English).

This essay has been approved by the department project committee.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this essay to God, my provider, my foundation and my life source. Thank you father for your faithfulness.

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ABSTRACT

Criminal behaviour, also referred to as social deviance, arises as a result of several factors which are predominantly social and environmental. However, despite the prominent role the individual's environment and social interactions play in the creation of a criminal, his psychological make-up or his consciousness has a large part to play in his development.

Crime and Punishment by Fyodor Dostoevsky can be viewed as a detective novel but not one detecting the criminal, but the motives behind the perpetration of the crime. Furthermore, it is a novel that centres on psychological observations.

Using the social-psychological approach, the study will aim to expose the intrinsic meanings of the novel, while explaining that committing a crime is as a result of several factors which include psychological and environmental factors [coincidence, situation etc]. Also, it will examine the efficacy of punishment and its ability to encourage a criminal consciousness or otherwise in a separate individual.

In addition, the study will provide an opportunity for a deeper understanding of psychological realism and it will expiate the link between psychology, sociology and literature in order to create a social impact as a result of a deeper understanding of the position of a criminal and his reasons for committing a crime.

Crime and Punishment presents different kinds of social deviance and their surrounding situations. Examining Raskolnikoff (the major character in the novel), we will see an individual who commits a murder as a result of several factors. He is plagued by a personality disorder, social factors and disorientation. In this novel, we are able to see a specific composition of both internal and external constituents which lead to criminal consciousness in the character of Raskolnikoff.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Man should be held responsible for his actions since he has the free will to choose between right and wrong; punishment should be applied specifically to discourage man from making a wrong choice.¹

Consciousness is the totality of the thoughts, feelings, impressions etc. of a person or a group relating to a particular sphere or collective awareness or sense.² A large part of a person's consciousness is usually as a result of sociological conditioning.

Criminal consciousness can be viewed as the possession of tendencies or inclination in an individual, which are criminally intended. Criminal consciousness is relevant to judicial judgement and in the judgement of ordinary deviant behaviours. The sociological term for illegal, immoral or eccentric behaviours is deviance. Deviance includes acts that are merely unconventional such as going barefoot on city streets as well as serious social problems such as crime and drug abuse. However, crimes are distinguished from other deviant acts because they are legally forbidden. To many observers, the causes of deviance seem simple enough because ordinary sensible people do not cheat; people who do must not be ordinary and sensible; there must be something wrong with them. To test this assumption, much research over the years has been devoted to finding out if there is such a thing as "the born criminal" and "the criminal mind."

Crime and Punishment is based on Dostoevsky's own terrifying experience of summary justice and the cruel penal system of Tsarist Russia. It is a tale set in the dingy tenements, back streets and bars of pre-revolutionary Saint Petersburg and concerns the actions of a murderer, Raskolnikoff, who in setting himself in the role of a superman of Napoleonic proportion, decides to commit homicide as a matter of principle. The novel, based on the interior of Raskolnikoff's mind, excites a striking source of interest. It captivates the reader, drawing him into its labyrinth of psychological depth. It is an apt representation of a social situation with its unequal social classes, and how that inequality affects the personalities of individuals and their reactions towards certain situations.

In describing the process by which criminal values are taken over by the individual, Edwin H Sutherland says;

*Criminal behaviour is learned and it is learned in interaction with others who have already incorporated criminal values and commitment opportunities including conditions favourable to the learning of such a role.*³

The subject 'crime' is a peculiar phenomenon in Dostoevsky's novel. However, Edward Wasiolek claims that crime is Dostoevsky's great theme not because he had a dark sympathy for crime but because it expresses and dramatizes beautifully the metaphysics of freedom.⁴

Fyodor Dostoevsky had a reputation as an author who gave an active psychological and philosophical insight into the depths of the human soul. This can easily be confirmed by a reading of his repertoire of novels. They concern themselves with the behavioural pattern of several people from different works of life. A concise paradigm of this situation is

Dostoevsky's The Possessed, which uses a large number of characters representing all classes of Russian society. In the novel, Dostoevsky shows how an idle interest in nihilism causes robbery, arson and murder in a Russian community. The plot is exceedingly complex but this very complexity tends to emphasise a similar quality in nineteenth century Russian life.⁵

Dostoevsky has a writing style of his own as a result of the influences he had both from the literary world and from his life. He has himself served as an influence to some writers. An example of which is the writer Faulkner who has himself acknowledged Dostoevsky's influence. Also with him are other diverse writers such as Charles-Louis-Philip, Malraux, Maurice, Sartre and Camus.

Crime and Punishment, the first of Dostoevsky's great long novels reveals the author's mastery of psychological observation and analysis.

One cannot ignore Dostoevsky's literary association with the traditions and influences of the European novel. He was influenced by Balzac, Dickens, Hugo and E.T.A. Hoffman. Nor can his ideology be detached from the western tradition of Christian and nationalist thought. There appear in Dostoevsky, versions of romantic historicism and folk worship that came to Russia with the great vogue of Schelling and Hegel in the question immediately preceding Dostoevsky's. Even Dostoevsky's psychological depth with his interest in the life of dreams and the splitting of personality is heavily indebted to the theories of romantic writers and doctors such as Reil and Carus.⁶

Nietzsche's superman, and Hegel informed the Napoleonic theory of Raskolnikoff. Friedrich William Nietzsche was a German philosopher who together with Soren Kierkegaard, shares the distinction of being a promoter of existentialism. Nietzsche developed ideas on 'The superman and the will to power' asserting that humans must learn to live without their gods or any other metaphysical consolations. According to him, like Goethe's Faust, humans must incorporate their devil and evolve beyond "good and evil". A great mass of cultured people in England seem unable to cross the "pontes asinorum" of morals: they cannot grasp the related fact that what is good for one is not necessarily good for society at large and that many people instinctively choose the bad when it is more profitable to themselves.⁷ All popular and superficial writers, however and all demagogues take for granted the opposite doctrines, namely that whatever is advantageous to a person, be he the most wicked and worthless creature on the face of the Earth, is therefore necessary for the good of the community and everyone instinctively chooses the right course as soon as he knows it.

Hegel George Wilhelm Friedrich was a German idealist philosopher, who has influenced most facets of philosophy. According to Hegel, reality is the absolute mind, reason or spirit, which manifests itself in both natural and human history. The mind is universal and therefore, cannot be identified with the mind of any particular person. Rather, each particular mind is an aspect of the world mind (Weltgeist) and the consciousness and rational activity of each person is a phase of the absolute itself. The activity of the mind is dialectical in nature. Hegel was preoccupied with triadic development, one phase demanding the next by inner necessity. In this development known as the Hegelian dialectic, the thesis is followed by its opposite the antithesis; the ensuing conflict between the two is brought together at a higher level as a new concept or synthesis which becomes the thesis of yet another triad.

*Common fancy puts the absolute far away in the world beyond. The absolute is rather directly before us, such that so long as we think, we must though without express consciousness of it always carry it with us and always use it.*⁸

In the novel Crime and Punishment, we discover a direct and obvious source of Raskolnikoff's notion of inferior and superior men: the superior ones having the right to commit breaches of morality while inferiors are obliged to mind their own business which is to stay put in the common rut. Hegel's world historical individuals such as Alexander the great, or Caesar, or Napoleon, the very names invoked by Dostoevsky's protagonist perform the grandiose task set for him by the 'wettgeist' irrespective of moral considerations.⁹

The model for all Russians was Pushkin. Like Dostoevsky, Pushkin was both a great virtuoso and something of a sphinx. Pushkin developed the art of exploring the world in terms of the experience and mental outlook of his own creations.¹⁰

Alexander Pushkin influenced Dostoevsky. Some of Pushkin's prose was read in the family circle. Pushkin gave birth to Dostoevsky in the world of the spirit. Pushkin dominates Dostoevsky's literary life from beginning to the end and the great writer he defended against his father in his youth is also the one to whom he devoted his last public utterance.

Raskolnikoff re-creates the murderous folly of Pushkin's Herman in The Queen of Spades, who is equally obsessed with an idée fixe and equally ready to murder to obtain wealth and power.¹¹

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGY AS AN ELUCIDATION

Social psychology is the study of how the behaviour of an individual is influenced by the actual, imagined or implied presence of other people.¹² This however, is the approach that will be employed in examining the work in question. At one time, psychologists waged various debates about how much of our behaviour is genetically determined and how much of it is learned. This was known as the nature controversy. We know that this “either or” question is rather meaningless since behaviour depends on the interaction between heredity and environment.¹³

A study of Dostoevski's Crime and Punishment will provide an opportunity for a deeper understanding of psychological realism, and it will expiate the link between psychology, sociology, and literature. This is in order to create a social impact as a result of a broader understanding of the position of a criminal and his reason for committing crimes.

Psychoanalytic criticism is a form of literary criticism, which uses some of the techniques of psychoanalysis in the interpretation of literature. Psychoanalysis is itself a form of therapy, which aims to cure mental disorder by investigating the interactions between conscious and unconscious elements of the mind.¹⁴

Psychoanalysis involves the study of human personality. It can also be referred to as the philosophy of humans. Psychoanalytic criticism involves the use of unconscious, repression, sublimation, condensation, etc. Also, it examines the ego, superego, and the id.

Sociology on the other hand, involves the understanding of what goes on in terms of social interaction. The sociological problem is not so much why some things go wrong from the

viewpoint of the authorities and the management of the social scene, but how the whole system works in the first place. What are its presuppositions and by what means is it held together? ¹⁵

We will not be far off if we see sociological thought as part of what Nietzsche called “the art of mistrust”. The sociological mysteries that lie behind the facade. The wish to penetrate these mysteries is an analogon to sociological curiosity. It should be noted however that this is a characteristic of literary criticism. Also, sociological understanding by itself does not necessarily lead to greater tolerance with respect to the foibles of mankind.¹⁶

Social psychology is often confused with sociology. Sociologists and social psychologists do share some common interests- they study how people behave in groups. Moreover, social psychology is a subfield of both its parent disciplines [psychology and sociology]. However, it is not a grand synthesis of the two fields. The subject matter and methods of social psychology differ from those of sociology. Most sociologists study the structure and functioning of groups from smaller groups to large groups (societies). The social psychologist is usually interested in the individual-how a person thinks about other people, is influenced by them and relates to them.¹⁷

Thus, while social psychologists are interested in groups, they generally want to ascertain how groups affect individual people or sometimes, how an individual can affect a group. For example, while many sociologists might be interested in how the racial attitudes of middle-class people as a group differ from those of lower social economical classes, the social psychologist will be more interested in how racial attitudes develop within the typical individual.

The essay also aims at revealing the uniqueness of Dostoevsky's form of writing by uncovering his characteristic devices and techniques as well as his relation to and use of existentialism. Jean Paul Sartre was probably the most famous as a representative of existentialism, a philosophical approach that emphasises among other things, the nebulousness of human condition. He wrote several phenomenological analyses of the imaginations and emotions, which culminated in his most important philosophical work, "Being and Nothingness". This means humans are essentially free and that any attempt by any individual person or philosophical theory that proposes otherwise, is a form of self deception or "bad faith". Existentialism is popularly known as a modern system of belief which says that man can only be free through full consciousness of his illogical position in a meaningless universe and that each person is alone and completely responsible for his or her actions. In French existentialism, Dostoevsky appears as a forerunner and crown witness. Dostoevsky's influence on diverse writers such as Charles-Louis-Phillips, Malraux, Sartre, and Camus is incalculable. The existentialists see only the 'underground man' in Dostoevsky and ignore the theist, the optimist, and even the utopian who looked forward to a golden age- a paradise on Earth while disparaging the socialist streams of collective utopia as a monstrous "ant hill" or "tower Babel".¹⁸

Also, Marxism will be considered especially with relation to the social types that are portrayed in the novel. The aim of Marxism is to show that society is divided into classes the 'have's' and 'have nots'. This situation places the classes into an irreconcilable antagonism. The antagonism, according to Max, would generate conflicts, which would ultimately sound the death knell of the exploiter class leading to the emergence of a classless society.¹⁹

Criminal behaviour and deviance have been a source of concern to all humans right from the beginning. The causes of deviance and the motives of criminals having been explored using different fields. Schools of thought have been created based on the criminal mind.

Criminology has delved into uncovering valuable information about the process of crime in modern societies. The question of punishment and how just it is, has raged on over the years. Organisations have been formed based on controversy about forms of punishment.

In the novel Crime and Punishment, two topics are to be addressed. The first one is the effect of de-orientation on human tendencies. The second one is the question of punishment and its efficacy or vice versa on the psyche of a criminal, and whether it starts off regeneration or not.

All the methods discussed in this chapter will be used in solving these questions and giving a better understanding of the criminal mind, bearing in mind that it does not necessarily foster leniency in the execution of justice against a criminal.

DOSTOEVESKY: A PATH TO PSYCHOLOGICAL REALISM

Fyodor Mikhailovich Dostoevsky was born in 1821 in Moscow. In 1867, he married Anna Grigoryevna (after the death of his first wife) who nursed him in his epilepsy; loyally bore his mania for gambling, helped him overcome his frequent depression brought on by dark and gloomy thoughts. His other great works were The Idiot (1868), The Devils (1872), A Raw Youth and The Brothers Karamazov (1880). He died in 1881 of a lung hemorrhage associated with an attack of epilepsy and was followed to his grave by 40,000 mourning Russians.

V.V. Zenkovsky says:

Raskolnikoff, Stavrogin and Ivan Karamazov all suffered in different ways because they stifled the sense of good (that is of God) in

*themselves. Freedom when it leaves us with ourselves alone reveals only chaos in the soul displaying our dark and ignoble impulses. It converts us into slaves of our own passions making us suffer torment.*²⁰

Dostoevsky points out forcefully to us that crime does not indicate any rational morality but on the contrary testifies (negatively) to the fact that in turning his back on the good, man loses something without which, he cannot live. The great novels of Dostoevsky's mature period; Notes from the Underground, The Insulted and The Injured, Crime and Punishment show the consequences of how the psychic organisation of Dostoevsky's characters create a deformation of the moral ideals. These grow out of the social misery of the modern metropolis. The vivid sketch is a good example of one of the techniques of insinuation that Dostoevsky uses. The device of what may be called the 'unexplained enigma' to which the knowing reader supplies the proper solution.²¹

Deviance may be excused if special characteristics of the violator and the situation are taken into account. However, psychological theories on deviance offer plausible explanations for the busy bizarre behaviours of even murderers. Most crimes however, are not obviously the result of mental illness.

Dostoevsky is a writer of world eminence for he knew how during a crisis of his country and the whole of the human race, to put questions in an imaginatively decisive sense. He created men whose destiny and inner life, whose conflicts are interrelations with other characters, whose attraction and rejection of men and ideas illuminated all the deepest questions of that age, sooner, more deeply and more widely than in average life itself.²²

In addition, Dostoevsky's school of thought which has permeated his writing style, could be traced to several other schools of thought, though with a single unifying thread running through them. The philosophies of Hegel, Nietzsche, Sartre, Marx etc. are strong influences on Dostoevsky. They all focus on the theme of man as a subject of his environment. In Dostoevsky's novels, he has brought to the fore his belief that several factors lead to the incubation of criminal thoughts and he has brought his arguments forward, using several characters and their individual voices.

NOTES

¹ O. Oloruntimehin, "Criminals are made not born: The myth and the Reality of Human Behaviour" (Inaugural Lecture), n.d.

² Lesley Brown Ed, The New Shorter English Dictionary and Historical Principles (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1993), n.p.

³ E.H. Sutherland. Ed, The Professional Thief (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1937). p.12

⁴ Edward Wasioleck, Dostoevsky: The Major Fiction (Massachusetts: Cambridge Mass M.I.T. Press, 1964), p.7.

⁵ Rene Welleck. Ed, Dostoevsky: A Collection of Critical Essays (Englewood Cliffs; N.J. Prentice Hall, 1962), p.7.

⁶ Philip Rahv, Essays on Literature and Politics, 1932–1972, (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1978), p.169.

⁷ Friedrich Nietzsche, Beyond Good and Evil (London: George Allen and Unwin Ltd, n.d.), p xii

⁸ William Wallace, The Logic of Hegel (London: Oxford University Press, 1873), P.50

⁹ Essays on Literature and Politics 1932-1972, p.302

¹⁰ Robert Lord, Dostoevsky: Essays and Perspectives (Berkley: University of California Press, 1976), p.61

¹¹ Joseph Frank, Dostoevsky; The Seeds of Revolt, (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1976), p.64

¹² Smith E. Ronald, Irwin Sarason and Babra R, Sarason Psychology: The Frontiers of Behaviour (New York: Harper and Row Publishers, 1986), p.584

¹³ Psychology: The Frontiers of Behaviour, P.68

¹⁴ Peter Barry, Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory (Manchester: Manchester University Press), p.115.

¹⁵ Peter L. Berger, Invitation to Sociology: A Humanistic Perspective, (USA: Doubleday and co, 1963), pp.49–50.

¹⁶ Invitation to Sociology: A Humanistic Perspective, p.42

¹⁷ David G. Meyers, Social Psychology (Holland: Hope College, 1987) p.4

¹⁸ Dostoevsky: A Collection of Critical Essays, p.8.

¹⁹ Dostoevsky: The Seeds of Revolt, p. 45.

²⁰ Dostoevsky: A Collection of Critical Essays, p.136.

²¹ Dostoevsky: The Seeds of Revolt, p. 220

²² Essays on Literature and Politics 1932-1972, p.138.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

THE RUSSIAN SOCIOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The background of Russian history is the great Eurasian plane bounded on the north by the Arctic Sea, on the east by the Plateau of Eastern Siberia, the Atai, Tarbagaitai and Tien-Shan mountains on the south by the Piedmont regions of Turkestan, the Caspian, the Caucasus and the Crimea.

Russian literature began with the penetration of Russia by Christianity in the late 10th century. As a result of this, most of its early literature was religious. At this time, Kiev was the capital and most important city in Russia. Early Russian Literature is said to belong to the Kievan period. Russians honor the poets Alexander Pushkin, who died in 1837, above all writers; but it was through great 19th century masters of prose fiction, especially Fyodor Theodore Dostoevsky, Leo Tolstoy and Ivan Turgenev, that Russian literature first gained the attention of foreign readers.

The heroic period had receded even further when Dostoevsky appeared and the bourgeois Society of Western Europe had consolidated itself. Napoleonic dreams had created inner and outer barriers, which were different from those that were erected in the times of Balzac and Stendhal. The Russia of Dostoevsky was beginning a social transformation. Russia was during that period a contemporary of Europe after 1848, with its disillusionment with the ideals of the 18th century and its dreams of renovation and reformation of the bourgeois society. The contemporaneity with Europe however rose in a pre-revolutionary period when the Russian “ancien-regime” still ruled unchecked. Nineteenth century Russians were

indifferent to the suffering of the masses. The world in which Dostoevsky grew up was lined in the shadows of Decemberist insurrection and suffered from the harsh police state atmosphere instituted by Nicholas. Later, Dostoevsky, on exile in Siberia, would meet the wives and families of the surviving Decemberists who had dedicated themselves to elevating the lot of the newly arrived unfortunates. These women had voluntarily followed their husbands to Siberia and their selfless devotion, as well as their unceasing efforts to soften the blows of fate for a new generation of political exiles, served as refutation of all theories, denying the existence of freewill, the possibility of moral and self sacrifice. This is aptly reflected in his novel Crime and Punishment in the character of Sonia (the prostitute).

The Russians have a concept of “the living life”, partly liturgical in origin and difficult to translate into Western European idiom. It is the “living life” that this Petersburg man from the underground is talking about and it is the basic ingredients that we have ignored to our cost.¹

Formal or orthodox sociologists are wont to define sociology as an essentially scientific, objective study of man in society. The study of social institutions, and of social processes. There is doubt if literature is doing anything different. Our study of literature reveals that it is also a discipline permanently concerned with man's social world, his adaptation and desire to change it. All literary genres attempt to recreate the social world of man's relation with his family, with politics, with the states in its economic or religious constructs. Literature delineates the role of man in his environment as well as the conflicts and tensions, between groups and social classes. In other words, it deals with much of the same social, economic, religious and political structure of the society as it is done in sociology.

THE RUSSIAN NOVEL

No Russian writer, whether Tsarist or Soviet, has been free or has felt free to express himself as he wished, while he lived and published in his own country. The principles of Tsarist censorship were to suppress anything that might tend to subvert the authority of the central government. Leo Tolstoi, was one of the major writers that was affected by this law.²

The reason why early writers were treated so abominably in Russia was that, in relation to propaganda they were important. Literature in the nineteenth century was a source of knowledge and a well of hope. Russian writers satisfied a demand not only for aesthetic experience, but also for ideas.³ In the great majority, they accepted the role of educator and uplifter. Gogol sought to improve morals, Turgenev, to instill respect for the enserfed folk, writers of the “Natural School” to expose social justice, Dostoevsky and Tolstoy, to find and preach a firm faith. Because their work and their messages were taken seriously by the people, the attention of the autocratic government was frequently drawn to these writers and sometimes they suffered from this.⁴

Russian prose fiction is a pale imitation of the European models. According to David. W. Gasperatti, in his book, The Rise of the Russian novel, he locates the origin of the Russian novel in indigenous writing. He shows how Russian writers use elements of native-inspired sub-culture - folklore, pulp fiction and the entertainment of carnival to subvert the conventions of foreign literature.⁵

The Russian novel according to O.B. Jegede (1998), in the nineteenth century, contributed to the fight for freedom. It was the only safe weapon with which writers fought a number of things like injustice and immorality in their societies. As the novel reacted to the social-political situations around it, it became a form of propaganda for progressive ideas. Two important works titled Resurrection and War and Peace (1868) by Leo Tolstoy played

important roles in Russia's resistance to the Nazi attack. In the same way, Fyodor Dostoevsky's Crime and Punishment (1866) protested against crime.⁶

To link politics with literature when speaking of contemporary Russia, is a natural procedure. All forms of literature are quite frankly and directly used by the Soviet government for political purposes.⁷

Literature means more to the average educated Russian, than it does to his western counterparts; books played no comparable part in the morale of Great Britain in the period where she stood alone against the Nazis. The Russians expect good books to be part of their lives.

In addition, the Russian novel is characterised by its interest in philosophy, history, psychology and aesthetics, ethnography, sociology, and so on. This was a form that the Russian novel picked up during the second half of the nineteenth century.

Much of the work of the proletarian novelists of the twenties was concerned with psychological realism and problems involved in remaking the world as reflected through the prism of the individual mind. The association of the proletarian writers urged upon its members, the necessity to 'show forth' the complex human psyche, with all his contradictions, elements of the past, seeds of the future, both conscious and subconscious.⁸

Also, the Russian novel explored regular themes, such as love and its sexual expression, unrequited love, the madness of jealousy, the suicides. They were at a time, characteristic of Turgenev's work. They were controlled and reduced after a while.

The psychology of characters acquired great importance to Russian writers of the mid-nineteenth century because it was found to be the psychology of wild social classes or at least of social groups. Therefore, the processes taking place in the souls of individual characters are a reflection of historical movement.⁹

DOSTOEVSKY AS A TYPIFIER OF THE RUSSIAN SOCIETY

Dostoevsky, one of the giants of Russian literature, made a serious impact on the literature of his period. Many opinions have been expressed concerning his character from both those who admire him, and from those that despise him.

Dmitri Merezhkovsky (1865–1941) began to elaborate his series of comparisons between Tolstoy and Dostoevsky (1926), Tolstoy the pagan, “the seer of the flesh”, with Dostoevsky, the Christian, “the seer of the spirit”. Merezhkovsky argued that Dostoevsky is not a realist, but a symbolist. Dostoevsky does not describe a social situation, but presents a tragedy of ideas; he is a prophet of a new religion embodied in works of art.¹⁰

This is a description of Dostoevsky as a symbolist writer and that is because rather than being concerned with the exact presentation of the society as it is, he prefers to present human psychology as it is. This can be noticed in the presentation of Raskolnikoff’s ideas and how they get refuted. This can also be seen as an ingredient of his polyphony. Although the external atmosphere of oppression and hard times helps to sharpen its reflexes and generate a sense of adventure, this alone did not account for the dramatic flavour of Russian life. Many Russians did behave like fictional characters partly because in their private affairs they are less conformist and regimented than their western counterparts.¹¹ Almost all the characters in Dostoevsky's novels cannot exactly be seen as contemporary individuals: Marmeladoff, Sonia, Alena Ivanovna, Raskolnikoff, Looshin etc They all have their own unique forms of consciousness.

The generations of writers that came of age between 1835 and 1850 produced the realistic novel that gave Russian literature universal recognition. The works of Turgenev, Dostoevsky

and Tolstoy have come to be regarded as the fullest expression of the “Russian soul and synonymous with Russia's message to the world. The specific qualities and philosophy were conditioned by the nature of the social groups that produced them.¹²

It is widely known that to the educated Russian, literature means a lot. During the nineteenth century it was an effective instrument of propaganda.

Dostoevsky can be seen as a means of penetrating into the hidden depths of human psychology and tearing off all the different kinds of veils and masks which conceal the nature and content of man's inner world.¹³ This is exactly what he succeeded in doing with the character of Raskolnikoff and that is one of the reasons why the novel is not one of detection of a crime, but one of the detection of the motive behind the crime.

V Ermilov repeatedly ranks Dostoevsky as one of the creators of world culture and lofty spiritual values whom all mankind hold in high regard. He refers to Lenin's interest in Dostoevsky and Maxim Gorki's high esteem for Dostoevsky's artistic genius. He cites Dostoevsky's name on a par with those of Leo Tolstoy, Pushkin and Gogol as one of those that constitute the pride and glory of Russian culture. More than everything else, Ermilov sees Dostoevsky's writings as a brilliant exposure and artistic revelation of the “terrible laws of the capitalist world”. The value of his works Ermilov believes lies in their “anti-bourgeois politics,” their humanism, their very passionate love for the “little” insulted and injured man, the depth and subtlety of their psychological analysis, and in the voice of conscience which resounds through them.¹⁴

This is evident in the creation of characters such as Sonia, Catherina, Marmeladoff, Raskolnikoff, and their dingy, poverty-stricken states.

Nicolay Bervadev (1874 - 1949) unquestionably has a profound grasp of the theological and philosophical implications of Dostoevsky's views and is by no means uncritical of some of his teachings: he does not for example, consider him “a master of discipline” but rather tries to make the concept of freedom the choice between good and evil, the centre of Dostoevsky’s thought as it is of his own thinking.¹⁵

The question of choice is a strong one in Dostoevsky’s writing. He concentrates on man’s freedom to choose between good and evil and this brings us to the question of a person’s consciousness. In this context, meaning his inclinations.

Dostoevsky’s pronouncements on literature in the novels Crime and Punishment, The Devils, The Idiot, A Raw Youth, The Brothers Karamazov as well as in The Diary of the Writer are traced in detail. As a critic, Dostoevsky is presented here in the role of a defender of the realistic ideals of Russian Literature and Art. Dostoevsky’s fidelity to the traditions of Pushkin and Gogol, his appeal to writers to study the real world intently, the statements about the importance of the typical as one of the basis for a realistic art, his struggle against liberal gentry ideals in art, against a naturalistic “photographism” and insipid copying of the external aspect of the subject is portraying with the attitude of serenity and awareness - all these factors, says Fridlender, makes Dostoevsky’s aesthetics progressive.¹⁶

A careful study of Dostoevsky’s novels would reveal his aversion to ‘photographism’ and an insipid copying of the external aspect of everyday life. This is because the situations he presents are not ‘everyday’ situations. This is bearing in mind that ‘everyday’ means normal or day-to-day life. Although Russians are viewed as non-conformist, his characters are not an

exact portrayal of that non-conformism. His characters' non-conformism is raised to higher degrees than the 'everyday' Russian life situation.

Dostoevsky's theological stand involves faith in God and advocacy for the involvement of God in individual deeds. His philosophical thought is that of existentialism. As a result, he tries to prove to us that the world is meaningless and it is only through the Christian faith that a level of meaning could come into life.

G.M Fridlander is a scholar, who has written several articles on Dostoevsky, which have appeared in Soviet journals as well as preferences to Dostoevsky's work notably The Idiot. He is also the author of a chapter entitled 'Dostoevsky the Critic' in the second volume 'History of Russian Criticism' edited by V.P. Gorodetski, A. Havretski and B.S. Medkh. In his introductory address, A. Surkov stressed the fact that Dostoevsky's works have become part of the treasure house of world culture. In his report, V. Ermilov termed Dostoevsky as one of the greatest writers of both Russian and World literature, whose heritage had become the property of all nations. The images created by Dostoevsky become the property of all nations. The images created by Dostoevsky, declared Ermilov, lie on the consciousness of all mankind. They have not faded; indeed they can never die.

In world literature, Dostoevsky's name ranks high. He is well esteemed and because of his vast knowledge in the realm of psychological realism he has managed to draw the attention of many critics, thereby increasing his popularity.

UNDERSTANDING DOSTOEVSKY

One way of defining Dostoevsky's genius according to Joseph Frank is to locate his ability to fuse his private dilemmas with those raging in the society of which he was a part. Also, to him, Dostoevsky felt that his own work was an attempt to grapple with the chaos of the present.¹⁸

If we are ever to understand Dostoevsky properly, we should do well to keep in mind, the precious capacity to the full intensity of his privacy emotions into what is essentially a matter of cultural and national concern.¹⁹

This is evident in works containing his biography sketches of everyday life, nor descriptive portraits of people and landscape, but rather, the psychological experiences of his characters, the hidden meaning of the events in their lives and the process of disclosing their ideas.²⁰

Grossman maintains that Dostoevsky differs from his contemporaries and other realist writers in his more complete reaction to the deeper processes of human consciousness of man's unconscious life, his incursion into the realm of psychological hypothesis and his creative insight into the world of his characters' thoughts and feelings.²¹

This is exactly what the novel Crime and Punishment is based on. It is the process of disclosing ideas of not just a major character, Raskolnikoff, but several others. For example, Peter Looshin, Svidrigailoff and Sonia.

G. Pospelov's opinion is that Dostoevsky's novels are oriented towards the future and bear the stamp of urbanism. They reflect the atmosphere of Petersburg life in the 1860s and 1870 with quick tempo, tension, overstrain and so on.²²

Dostoevsky's novels show the negative effects of "future" urbanism which is a direct mark of the rise of secularism, science, technology and industry, decline in the impact of religion (Godlessness) and so on. This results in individualism, and other forms of "The study of self".

Like other writers, due to societal shifts and acquisition of knowledge, Dostoevsky was prone to a change of views, which happened quite often in his lifetime. These were recorded and written out in critiques about him.

Dostoevsky abandoned his favourite theme, that of insulted and injured folk and began to resort to subjectivism and arbitrariness in his description of reality and as a result, he reached some extremely reactionary conclusions. Postulating a mutual hostility between the nihilists and society, Dostoevsky on the one hand defamed the entire Russian liberal and democratic movement, while on the other; he began to praise the existing order of things. Whereas in his previous novels, the atheists came under the fire of his criticism. He tried to account for all social vices in terms of loss of faith in God. Finally, his undeniable mastery of psychological analysis manifested aspects of the human soul. Therefore, Maxim Gorki was not being unreasonable when he called The Devils a sadistic morbid work.²³

An important method of understanding Dostoevsky is by taking a close look at the things that have influenced his thinking and mode of writing.

Digging into Dostoevsky's biography, Guerard Albert uncovers that Dostoevsky's father was murdered by some Serfs. He gained fame at a very young age, he had criticism from Belinsky. He was arrested for subversive activity and almost executed, and then had a sudden reprieve. He spent years in fetters in Siberia among generally hostile convicts; he was constantly humiliated by his incessant debts and always had to write frenziedly against critics. All these made A.J. Guerard concludes that Dostoevsky is a disturbed writer. It was a wonder that he was as sane and self disciplined as he was. He wrote focusing on the general question of the writer's conscious and unconscious understanding of the psychic process and unusual behaviour.²⁴

This has been speculated to be responsible for his interest in unusual characters and different forms of human psychology. However, there is no absolute certainty that this is the major influence on his work.

Dostoevsky's knowledge of almost all the different types of novels from the psychological novel, the utopian novel, the gothic novel, the crime novel, novels set in monasteries, sentimental and epistolary novels, novels in form of memoirs and confessions, novels of character and travel-mates, novels about artists and musicians, even the novel chronicle, and the novel pamphlet, the biographical novel and the novel expose - all this very rich literary knowledge supplied Dostoevsky with materials for his own art. All these varieties of the novel are woven together and blended in a unique manner in the new novelistic genre, which made Dostoevsky's name great and renowned in the history of Russian and world literature.²⁵

This versatility is evident in the novel Crime and Punishment. It is a mixture of the psychological novel, and the novel of detection, novel of character, the philosophical novel etc.

CRIME AND PUNISHMENT

Dostoevsky's experiences as a convict and rank and file soldier were also reflected in Crime and Punishment, one of the most outstanding works in world literature. In this novel, together with a protest against the existing order, we find an agonized quest for new forms of life, a new society and another kind of man. Two systems of thoughts and two spiritual types are compared and contrasted. Raskolnikoff's individualism and Sonia Marmeladoff's loving and submissive outlook. Raskolnikoff's ethical code, which is based on atheism, allows him to transgress the norms of social behaviour. Regarding himself as a bearer of new ideas to act against established laws. The writer has invested this figure with an unprecedented richness of content and brilliance. In Raskolnikoff a severely logical reasoning faculty blends with a very subtle analysis of the human soul with the resulting exposure of the complete unsoundness the way he has chosen to follow and the fundamental falsity of his extreme individualism. But Sonia's way of submission was justified by her deeds. She endured poverty, sorrow, hunger, humiliation and mockery without raising a single objection or protest like an eternal victim, she could only weep.

The idea of a new man in new forms of social life finds expression at the end of the novel in Raskolnikoff's dream of the catastrophe that is destined to befall the world of his time. The dream ends with the idea that during this impending collapse of human society, only a few pure chosen souls will be saved, who will be entrusted with the task of founding a new human race and a new life.²⁶

The aim of literature, according to Marxist criticism, is not just to reflect. The aim of literature, according to Marxist criticisms, is not just to reflect society but also to improve it. This is well adhered to in the novel Crime and Punishment.

Dimitri Pisarev (1840-68) the most violent of the 'radical critics', realized that 'Crime and Punishment' 1868 was an attack on the revolutionaries. While praising the author's humanistic and artistic power, he tried to fend off the implications of Dostoevsky's anti-nihilistic message by bluntly arguing that Raskolnikoff's theorist had nothing in common with those of the revolutionary youth and that 'the root of Raskolnikoff's illness was not in the brain but in the pocket'.²⁷

Even in the novel Raskolnikoff makes it obvious that he does not commit his crime because of money. If he were actually poverty driven he would have at least counted the money he stole.

An unsigned article in Pravda February 6, 1956 entitled 'a great Russian Writer' examines all of Dostoevsky's major works, from the standpoint of his contradictions. Crime and Punishment for example, is seen here as a trial of class society conducted by his art. It is alleged that his novel castigates the inhumanity of the capitalist system and its images of people who have been deprived of any and all prospects of a better future in life. According to the author of this article, the novel's weaknesses are that it is devoid of even a gleam of hope, that it denies the existence of any possibilities of a social struggle and that it glorifies Christian humility and suffering. Identifying the writer with his character, the article rebukes Dostoevsky for the false accusation it claimed he had made up against the revolutionaries of the last century. It charged that the novelist had passed off the arch-individualistic revolt of Raskolnikoff, a revolt which the article termed was 'bourgeois-anarchistic', it was true nevertheless, the article conceded, that even in the book, the harsh veracity of Dostoevsky's scenes of bourgeois society trigger the effects of his reactionary symbolising and aroused in

the reader an ‘indomitable hatred for a social system which oppressed, insulted and injured all that was best in humanity.’²⁸

The novel is a castigation of the capitalist system. Also, it succeeds in portraying individuals who have been deprived of even opportunities to have better lives. In accordance with the Pravda article, the novel glorifies Christian humility, and erases the possibility of a revolution or struggle. This view is opposed to the earlier view that Raskolnikoff’s last dream predicted the founding of a new human race and a new life.

Despite their nasty ‘underground’ and ‘Karamazov-like’ traits, many of Dostoevsky’s leading figures are tenaciously attached to life, and it is precisely their intuition of nothingness barely hinted at by their author, which feeds their cult of life. Raskolnikoff, as he wanders along the streets, is nevertheless struck by the following thought:

“where is it that I’ve read that someone condemned to death says or thinks an hour before his death, that if he had to live on some high rock or on such a narrow ledge that he’d have room only to stand and the clean, everlasting darkness, everlasting tempest, around him if he had to remain standing on a square yard of space all his life, a thousand years, an eternity it were better to live than to die at once! Man is a vile creature’... And vile is he who calls him vile for that.”²⁹

Mikhail Bakhtin has made some striking comments on the polyvalent nature of Dostoevsky’s style which in his view is always oriented in relation to a possible interlocutor. By this, Bakhtin means that the utterances of Dostoevsky’s narrators or characters are never simply

univocal descriptive reports or monologue utterances expressing the point of view of one or another character. Their words always contain implicit or overt references to a network of other possible responses and points of view. Dostoevsky's language, Bakhtin argues, is always 'dialogic' in this sense, even when no actual dialogue is taking place; he illustrates his contention with a wealth of perceptive detail.³⁰

This is a view that has not been challenged. The polyphonic nature of Dostoevsky's novel makes for an unravelling of several different ideas, without the author's voice taking precedence over all these ideas. The reader is left to make his choice at the end of the novel. Dostoevsky's novels are not entirely understood during the first reading. It takes a good close study to understand them, and when they are understood, several points are recognised in them.

*'There is hardly a paragraph in Dostoevsky which does not contain some paradox. He is a maze of paradoxes and even the most trivial of them needs no very powerful microscope to grow into bewildering proportions.'*³¹

F.I. Evnin, in his article, shared with his readers his specific observations on certain particular features of the writer's poetics.

I do not describe cities, domestic furnishings, people's everyday way of life, nor their jobs and connections. Nor as a matter of fact, do I have any time to spend doing detailed scenes of our own little milieu. Naturally, since my story takes place not in heaven, but down here in our world, I cannot avoid sometimes, touching in a purely pictorial

*way, of everyday aspects of life in our province, but I want to make it clear right from the start that I will do so only to the extent that I am forced to say the most urgent necessity and I am not going to start devoting myself to the specifically descriptive part of our modern way of life.*³²

‘Dostoevsky limits himself to giving only a few details which he, so to speak, drops in passing’.³³

Dostoevsky is a descriptive writer. Though his descriptions are mostly psychological, he also manages to portray his immediate society well. Especially when he's trying to prove a point, for example, the poverty-stricken state of the masses in Russia as portrayed Crime and Punishment.

Dostoevsky's innovations, first demonstrated in The Double with this creation of a new form, the interior dialogue reached its apogee in his wonderful mastery designed to reveal the dialectic of the soul of the processes of a divided consciousness and split personality in the scene between Ivan Karamazov and the devil. This scene is the supreme achievement of literary art, with respect to the self-analysis and self-questioning of a single character.³⁴

The interior dialogue is a normal phenomenon in humans who are given to deep thinking and who are deeply intelligent. It is an easy way of bringing into the fore, the psychological state of a character, as well as his type of consciousness.

Dostoevsky deliberately accentuated the unexpected in his characters' behaviours so that they should disrupt the lives of others around them. Each character is supplied with his own individual existential germ, which ripens in the dark and secret corners of the soul until one day, it breaks through into actuality.

Dostoevsky's characters are like creatures from different worlds, thrown into the same world. Their responses strike in the world they find themselves, turn out to be mere echoes. Whenever, there is a conflict within a single individual, the conflict erupts as a crime occurs in circumstances in which half of the personality overrides the other. Raskolnikoff was persuaded of the unfeasibility of his plan to murder the old hag of a usurer. In the end, he commits the crime automatically as if his thoughts and actions were being guided by some power beyond his rational control. The interpretation of crime in Dostoevsky tallies with important sections of abnormal psychology and criminal psychology.³⁵

In conclusion, Dostoevsky as a writer has succeeded in accomplishing the most important aim of literature and that according to the Marxist critics is to correct and improve the society. Dostoevsky's novels cannot just be read for entertainment, because it gets the reader thinking. Dostoevsky has succeeded in creating a blend between literature that serves to inspire deep thought, and 'Literature that is purely for entertainment'. For instance, in viewing a juxtaposition between Crime and Punishment and James Joyce's A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man; the latter is a novel meant basically for intellectuals and it does not serve any entertainment function. Whereas Crime and Punishment does both at the same time.

However, there is a major point that is not well settled in the novel. Raskolnikoff's punishment was not severe enough. A man possessing such ideals should not be left free to roam the streets. According to the novel, Raskolnikoff claimed that 'the cause of all was his wretched condition, his misery and helplessness and his desire to secure, at least, the means of starting his career.'³⁶

The judges seemed to be influenced by the absence of defence on the culprit's part and his evident desire to make no extenuation of his crimes'. He claimed to have repented but what

the judges did not put into consideration is the fact that he could do it again and another pair of innocent people could end up losing their lives. Especially owing to the fact that Raskolnikoff's consciousness is inherently criminal.

NOTES

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- ² L.O. Bamidele, Literature and Sociology (Ibadan: Stirling Holden Publishers, n.d.), p.4
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- ⁹ Vladimir Seduro, Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today (Belmont, Massachusetts: Nordland Publishing Company, 1975), p.223
- ¹⁰ Dostoevsky. A collection of critical essays p.5
- ¹¹ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.281
- ¹² Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.283
- ¹³ Dostoevsky The seeds of Revolt p. 282
- ¹⁴ Dostoevsky The seeds of Revolt p.66
- ¹⁵ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.65
- ¹⁶ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.342
- ¹⁷ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.305
- ¹⁸ Edward Wasioleck, Dostoevsky. The Major Fiction (Massachusetts: the M.I.I press, 1964), p.xii
- ¹⁹ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.46

- ²⁰ Dostoevsky: a collection of critical essays p.52
- ²¹ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.34
- ²² Dostoevsky: Essays and Perspectives p. vii
- ²³ Dostoevskys: Essays and Perspectives p.viii
- ²⁴ Fyodor M. Dostoevsky, Notebooks of F.M. Dostoevsky (Academia, 1935), p. 247
- ²⁵ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.65
- ²⁶ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.101
- ²⁷ Dostoevsky: Essays and Perspectives p.204
- ²⁸ Dostoevsky's Image in Russia Today p.34
- ²⁹ Dostoevsky. The Seeds of Revolt p.155
- ³⁰ Dostoevskys: Essays and Perspectives p.viii
- ³¹ Dostoevskys: Essays and Perspectives p.vii
- ³² Fyodor M. Dostoevsky, Notebooks of F.M. Dostoevsky (Academia, 1935), p.249
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CHAPTER 3

CRIME AND THE SOCIETY

Crime is as old as man. In Genesis 4 vs 8, it was stated that Cain had killed his brother Abel. Thus Cain committed an act, which is termed homicide by the criminal law. Folklores of several societies in the past such as ancient Greek, Rome and Medieval Europe have reflected man's concern with the crime problem. However, the understanding of crime and the criminal did not engage the attention of scholars until after the enlightenment in Europe. Scholars of diverse callings were prompted to consider the crime problem during this period as a result of the operation of the legal system in Europe. Punishment was arbitrary and barbarous. This led to the development of different schools of thoughts in criminology and the emergence of systematic principles for the understanding of crime and the criminal.¹

One of the schools formed was 'the positive school of criminology'. Ceasare Lombroso (1835 to 1909) an Italian, led the school. He was trained as a psychiatrist. The Darwinian theory of human and evolution inspired his approach to the study of crime. The positive school laid emphasis on the need to focus attention on the criminal rather than the crime. Lombroso is remembered today as the father of modern criminology since all attempts to explain criminal behaviour to date have been reactions and counter-reactions to his ideas as well as efforts to refine his approach.²

An idea was formulated 'the born criminal' which is based on an assumption that the population of any society at any point in time can be distinctly divided into the criminal and non-criminal. Traits (biological, physiological and psychological) which were found in the criminal group were believed to be different from those found in the non-criminal group and so should account for the criminality of the criminal group. The idea of the 'born criminal' is inadequate in examining criminal behaviour. So also is the positive school.³

Criminology, which is the systemic study of crime, the criminal and the treatment of the offender, involves inputs from various disciplines such as Medicine, Psychology, Law, Economics and Sociology. Criminology as a special field within sociology has uncovered valuable information about the processes of crime in modern society.⁴

Most serious crimes are violations of mores, the norms of behaviour that are considered vital to preserving society. They fall into three broad categories; crimes against persons, crimes against property, and crimes against morality. Crimes against persons consist of domestic violence, child abuse and wife-beating etc. Of all crimes against property, theft is the most common. Modern computer technology has greatly increased the opportunity of embezzlement. Crimes against morality; the most controversial section of the criminal law consists of the statutes enforcing conventional standards of moral behaviour. Examples are gambling, obscenity, prostitution, public drunkenness, and the possession of certain drugs. These offences are often called victimless crimes, since they are voluntary activities that typically harm no one but those who commit them.⁵

In examining a criminal one could use Freud's personality analysis which says that an experience which has occurred during infancy and childhood, could set an adult personality. He described a negative life-destroying tendency in the human psyche which he calls 'Thanatos' and which he postulated in an attempt to explain the carnage of the first world war.⁶

There are different kinds of criminals. There are The Respectables, amateur thieves are quite often white collar-workers who steal on the job. White-collar crimes include embezzlements, expense accounts padding, and taking bribes and kickbacks. Embezzlers and other white-collar criminals do not earn their living by stealing. They rarely have a criminal record or associate with people who do. Others are shoplifting, theft of souvenirs, tax evasion etc.

Professional criminals do not commit crimes on impulse or as an occasional sideline, but as a regular way of making a living. They never have honest jobs, but devote all their working time to their illegal occupation.

Criminal organisations often regarded as Organized crimes are a group of criminals organized for illegal purposes- to distribute heroin or operate a number of rackets, for example, the Mafia. Others are corporations and political groups.⁷

From the sociological perspective, the causes of crime and violence lie deep within the social structure. Poverty, unequal opportunities for the minorities, a cultural emphasis of ‘making it’, which is cited as one of the reasons for the murders which are committed in the novel Crime and Punishment.

PLOT STRUCTURE OF THE NOVEL

The novel Crime and Punishment is a psychological account of a crime. A young man of middle class origin, who is living in dire need, is expelled from the university. From very superficial and weak thinking, having been influenced by certain ‘unfinished’ ideas in his head, he decides to get himself out of a difficult situation quickly by killing an old woman, a usurer and widow of government services. He is then struck by monomania, depression etc. His mother and sister come into the novel when he gets back to his room and finds them waiting for him. Emotionally, he is imbalanced so he places them in the care of his friend Razoumikhin.

Svidrigaloff, (Raskolnikoffs double), is introduced into the novel. He had caused Donia (Raskolnikoffs sister) great suffering while she had been in his employ as a governess.

Raskolnikoff meets Sonia the prostitute, gets involved in deep conversations with her and plans to tell her who committed the murder. Tortured by his own mind, Raskolnikoff goes to

the police station where Pofirus (the magistrate) torments him with questions and ironic statements.

Later, Raskolnikoff confesses his crime to Sonia and admits that in killing the two women he actually destroyed himself. Svidrigaloff, having overheard the confession, discloses his knowledge to Raskolnikoff. Believing that Pofiry suspects him of the murders, and realising that Svidrigaloff knows the truth, Raskolnikoff finds life unbearable. Convinced that Dounia would have nothing to do with him, Svidrigaloff gives her a large sum of money and ends his life with a pistol.

Raskolnikoff turns himself over to the police and is sentenced to eight years in Siberia. Sonia follows him and with her help, he begins his regeneration.

The plot in this novel is subjected to a rich flow of mental states. It is difficult therefore not to know something of the internal forces motivating Raskolnikoff, for they are on display.⁸

In the novel, Dostoevsky is said to be the first novelist to have fully accepted and dramatized the principle of uncertainty and indeterminacy in the presentation of characters. It manifests itself as a kind of hyperbolic suspense in the plot of the novel.

THEMATIC PREOCCUPATIONS IN CRIME AND PUNISHMENT

The novel begins with characters who are as sensitive as hunchbacks, quick to take offense, terrible in their hurt, boundless in their vanity, unforgiving in their grudges, and delighted in their pettiness. It begins and turns on the word 'hurt'. Hurt always generates another hurt. Every hurt person wants immediately to make someone else bear his hurt. Thus, our abnormally sensitive hero it's always paying back

someone for something. For example Raskolnikoff wants to pay society back for his poverty and neglect of his fine qualities. The circle of hurt-and-be-hurt is the basic psychological law of Dostoevsky's world. A few refuse to pay back because of the nature of their consciousness; 'the idiot', Sonia, Alyosha. They are of another world. Dostoevsky's hero not only pays back for the hurt he suffers, but he also looks for hurt to suffer. The vicious circle of 'hurt and be hurt' is something of his making. He is at once provoker and sufferer, prosecutor and victim.⁹

The novel also discusses the problem of freedom of choice, which in this case has been 'imposed' on man. The dialectic of man posed between nihilistic freedom and God, which Dostoevsky takes up in Crime and Punishment, shows that hedonistic bliss is bought at the price of the freedom of the individual.¹⁰

Crime and Punishment is the trying out of the consequences of a "freewill" unleashed on society and at the same time an attempt to find a force to restrain a freewill (which is God).

Crime and Punishment as a result, is the drama of terrible consequences that follow an unleashed will and the groping for psychological and metaphysical roots of God in reality.¹¹

Under this point, we come across the theories of individualism, which socialist thinkers believe signified autonomy, freedom, and sacredness of the individual. These values, in some countries such as France, had taken a negative oppressive and anarchic form signifying individual isolation and social dissolution. This is well represented in Raskolnikoff's consciousness. Other great themes are questions of transgression, guilt and suffering, freedom and authority, "new men", positivism, socialism, the difficulty of belief and the tragedy of unbelief, religion and morality, the ill effects of disorientation on human behaviour and criminal consciousness, which is what will be discussed in this chapter.

CHARACTER PORTRAITS IN THE NOVEL

In examining Raskolnikoff's consciousness, there are certain characters in the novel; whose consciousness have to be examined for Dostoevsky did not build Raskolnikoff's character in isolation, especially since a socio-psychological reading is what will be used in the analysis of this novel.

First, Rodion Romanovitch Raskolnikoff is the main character of the novel, who murders an old pawnbroker, to prove a point. He is remarkably handsome with beautiful dark eyes, dark hair, taller than average, slim and well built. Dostoevsky uses his name symbolically in this novel. Between 1654 and 98, during the crisis of muscovite civilization, the church and the commercial class, two most conservative and traditional forces-were losing their importance. Of all the causes that hastened the decline of the church, the schism that broke out in 1654 was the most effective. The rebellious factor responsible for this, became known as the Raskolniks (schismatic) or old believers.¹²

Raskolnikoff in Crime and Punishment, believes himself to be another kind of criminal altogether, one acting from rational calculation and in interest of a higher idea; the irony of self deception is among the finest effects of the book. Raskolnikoff describes his psychological person as;

*“I am excessively vain, envious, ill-disposed and vindictive
and what's more inclined to folly.”*

He is portrayed in this novel as one suffering from schizophrenia and plagued by dementia. He is capable of both good and bad deeds. He is also viewed as an unrepentant criminal and one who cannot shoulder the emotional trauma that comes with committing a crime as heinous as murder.

Archadius Ivanovitch Svidrigailoff, Raskolnikoff's double, is described as one who has flaxen hair, pale blue eyes, red lips and a mask-like face; he carouses in the dens of the city, seduces young girls, and mysterious crimes are reported about him. He embodies all the artifice and melodrama of the Gothic villain, but he is also something more. As

Raskolnikoff's double who commits crimes without feeling any pangs of conscience, the terror and artifice, which was artifice and melodrama, became at least in part, the terror and the mystery of the wheel and the moral nature of man.

Sophia (Sonia) Semenovna, had a thin pale face, her small nose and chin, were more or less pointed and angular, the whole face was not quite in harmony, hence she could not be called pretty. Her blue eyes were so limp that on becoming animated they gave to the whole face such an expression of kindness that people felt involuntarily attracted to her. She seemed much younger than her real age. Although only 18, she could almost be taken for a lassie.

Everything in Sonia's house denoted poverty. She is one of the characters Dostoevsky uses to mirror the Russian proletariat situation. She has a kind heart and genuine concern for the welfare of her family. She is characterised by patience and a quiet but determined love for Raskolnikoff.

Marmeladoff, a civil clerk, because of misfortune, goes from bad to worse; he ends up destitute in the capital and his daughter is forced into prostitution; his wife who had come from a good family, becomes consumptive and the children go hungry. Marmeladoff at the Tavern when we first met him is described as a drunk with a bloated greenish face, puffy eyelids, hysterical eyes and ruffled hair. The Marmeladoff subplot is almost a paradigm of a sentimental situation, which has already influenced many of Dostoevsky's earlier works. Marmeladoff is an example of what Dostoevsky had once referred to as "self-inflicted" suffering.

Peter Petrovitch Loosin (Dounia's fiance) is a calculating manipulator. He didn't expect his end in the novel. He had been too presumptuous and had reckoned too much in his own power and on the helplessness of his victims. He is described as a 45 year-old man and tolerably good looking. Pulcheria Alexandrovna (Raskolnikoff's mother) describes him as stern, haughty, and even rude. In his visitation to Raskolnikoff he is described as having an affected air and a pompous carriage. He is vain, selfish, cold, calculating and boorish etc. He is insensitive towards people's feelings and uses them for his own purposes. He deliberately and cruelly slandered Sonia so as to be able to reconcile with Donia by showing them that Sonia is a social and moral outcast. He is also described as a very malicious individual. He is a member of the rich [bourgeois] and believes in subjecting those below him to his will.

Pophyrus Petrovich, the examining magistrate, is in charge of the things that were pledged with the old woman after she died. He is very intelligent, especially in psychological dealings. Raskolnikoff hates Pophyrus. He hates him beyond all expression and what he dreads, is lest he might show his hatred. He is one of the characters that Dostoevsky spun, that prodded Raskolnikoff on to his confession. He suspects Rakolnikoff of the murder and thus uses taunts and threats as well as other psychological means to get Raskolnikoff to admit his guilt.

Alena Ivanovna has sharp evil eyes, a pointed nose, hair smoothed out with grease and a flannel rag wrapped around a neck that looks like a chicken leg. She is not just a victim, but also the kind of victim Raskolnikoff needs. For him, she represents the heart of a corrupt society against which he revolts. Her image is almost mythical: a kind of minotaur devouring the prey of society until the white knight is able to destroy her. She is Gothic yet she is real

and she is so because she answers to one of the deceptive notions of Raskolnikoff: the killing of evil to do good. For this reason Raskolnikoff needs a useless evil; in her active hurting of good lives and exploitation of her sister, Raskolnikoff finds the useless arbitrary evil he needs. Moreover Alena exploits people so that praises to her soul may be sung after she is dead.¹³

Nothing astonished Dostoevsky more in his own world and in the world of his characters than the endless transformations the self could undergo using for his own purposes any impulse no matter how good, the infinite refinement of the mind no matter how evil. For the hero who does not understand the full implications-Raskolnikoff- the good act without God is self-deception. For the hero who knows what he's doing,-Svidrigailoff- the good act without God is an exquisite weapon for manifesting one's will over others.

CRIMINAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE NOVEL

Criminal consciousness, which is the possession of inclinations, which are inherently criminal, is a prevalent feature in the novel. Possession of criminal consciousness is usually detected through a person's speech, thoughts and dreams, behavioural pattern, beliefs and actions. Difference in consciousness is what makes Raskolnikoff a murderer and Sonia a prostitute and not a murderer. It is what makes Raskolnikoff afflicted by guilt and a stricken conscience, and it is what makes Svidrigailoff unaffected by his crimes.

Consciousness is innate. Each person can only experience his or her unconsciousness. However we all realise that other people are conscious too because they can tell us they are. In fact the soul intention of consciousness is verbal acknowledgement. Verbal behaviour defines consciousness. Consciousness can also be seen as a consequence of abilities to communicate internally with us and externally with others.¹⁴

Several questions have been asked about the criminal mind and several answers given. While some psychologists believe criminal behaviour is inherited, some believe it is acquired from social and environmental factors. Some believe that there has to be the possession of some tendencies in a criminal that are inherently criminal. This results in the fact that one cannot isolate social and environmental factors from the creation of a criminal mind. Therefore one of the factors involved in the making of a criminal is a merger between a criminal consciousness and disorientation.

Frank Tannenbaum, several decades ago, vividly expressed the point that criminals acquire their values and skills;

It takes a long time to make a good criminal, many years of specialised training and much preparation. But training is something that is given to people. People learn in a community where the materials and the knowledge are present. A craft needs an atmosphere saturated with purpose and promise. The community provides the attitudes, the point of view, the philosophy of life, the example, the motive, the contacts, the friendships, the incentives. No child brings these into the world. He finds them here and available for use and elaboration. The community gives the criminal his materials and habits just as it gives the Doctor, the Lawyer, the Teacher, and the candlestick maker theirs.¹⁵

Sometimes criminals are not even aware of the reasons why they commit crimes. To explain why an incident happened, or why a deed was done, you have to understand that people's actions are caused by different factors. For example, economic hardships, family problems, the situation at hand, the person's psyche or psychological make-up, and other forms of frustration. Not forgetting that in general usage, frustration refers to an unpleasant feeling produced by unfulfilled desire (as is the case with Raskolnikoff). When crimes are classified according to the kinds of offences that are committed and the reasons, it is clear that different explanations are needed to account for apparently identical client crimes. The respectable teller who embezzles from the bank, for example, denies that the theft is wrong and tries to justify it with a good excuse. When an expert forger commits the crime however, the motives and justification are very different: theft is a way of making a living. Since the underlying causes of the two criminal acts are so different, each is best explained by a different theory. Furthermore, the different causes of crime call for different social responses. A man who murders his wife in a blind rage is not treated in the same way as a mafia hitman who kills on the job, and neither is regarded in the same light as the corporate executives responsible for killing their customers with unsafe products. Attempts to prevent such murders also take different forms: for the violent husband, a crisis intervention program to help him cope with family problems; for the professional killer, prison or other radical punishments; for the indifferent manufacturer, a stiff fine for violating product safety standards.

Sutherland in explaining criminal behaviour and reasons for it said:

Though criminal behaviour is an expression of general needs and values, it is not explained by those general needs and values, since non-criminal behaviour is an expression of the same needs and

values. Thieves generally steal in order to secure money, but likewise honest labourers work in order to secure money. The attempts by many scholars to explain criminal behaviour by general drives and values, such as the happiness principle, striving for social status, the money motive or frustration, have been and must continue to be futile since they explain lawful behaviour as completely as they explain criminal behaviour.

Criminal behaviour requires a specialised environment if it is to flourish. Some of the specific components of systems organized for the socialisation of the potential criminal are; criminal role models, who are success-models and former members of the lower class. Many accounts suggest that the lower class adults who have achieved success by illegitimate means, not only are highly visible to young people in slum areas but often are willing to establish relationships with these youths. In Raskolnikoff's case, his role models were Napoleon, Alexander the great etc.

Learning alone does not ensure that the individual can or will perform the role for which has been prepared. The social structure must also support the actual performance of the role. To say that the individual must have the opportunity to discharge a stable criminal role, as well as to prepare for it, does not mean that the role preparation necessarily takes place in one stage, and role performance in a succeeding stage. Their apprentice may be afforded opportunities to play out a particular role at various points in the learning process. For example, some children make a game of shoplifting before they become real shoplifters. It is noted in Crime and Punishment, that Raskolnikoff rehearses his crime beforehand. Also the situations are mysteriously easy. In fact they are so easy that he says, "There's more of the

devil in this than my design". What happens before he makes this statement is that, when he gets to where he was supposed to get the hatchet, he does not find anything there. But somehow, he gets another hatchet. It said that the occurrence gives him fresh courage. The presence or absence of integrative relationships is another factor responsible for criminal behaviours. Unless the carriers of criminal or controversial values are closely strong to one another, stable criminal roles cannot develop. The criminal, like the occupant of a controversial role, must establish relationships with other categories of persons all of whom contribute in one way or another to the successful performance of criminal activity. In Raskolnikoff's case it could be said that an absence of people with criminal roles surrounding him, is what makes him repentant. He is close to people who have loving personalities. For instance, Sonia, Dounia, his mother, Razoumkhim etc. Svidrigailoff and Looshin, those with negative characteristics, are not that close to him. As a result, there is no one to reassure him that what he did was normal. Meanwhile it could be said that, when he wanders off his regular path, and he overhears a discussion about the old woman's evil nature; when the student was involved in a discussion with an officer, was describing her, he is provided with all the encouragement he needs:

"But I tell you what I would do. I would kill that damnable old hag, and take all she possessed of, without any qualm of conscience- a thousand good deeds and enterprises could be carried out and upheld with the money this old woman has bequeathed to a monastery. A dozen families might be saved from hunger, want, ruin, crime and misery – kill her I say, take it from her and dedicate it to the service of humanity."

As has been earlier mentioned, crimes are committed for various reasons. While some kill as part of business transactions, such as the 'crime trust', which murders impersonally and solely for business,¹⁶ some kill for personal reasons as a reaction to societal pressures for instance, Raskolnikoff, who wants to revolt because of the crushing conditions in which he lives. It is a representation of the way (in Marxism) the proletariat feel towards the bourgeois. The fault that lies with his acts of revolution was with the murderers that came with it. Taking a human life is legally and morally wrong.

An instance in Nigeria, is Lawrence Anenih of Benin who was a notorious robber. He robbed from the rich, and used to share his loot with the poor people in the marketplace in Benin. To the poor masses of Benin, he was their saviour, but the fact remained that he was a criminal. Robbery and murder are serious crimes; therefore he was hunted down by the law-enforcement agencies and killed.

Using Anenih's example, the difference in consciousness is what makes him a robber and what makes the people at the marketplaces, commonplace individuals. His belief tells him that he can make a difference by robbing and sharing the money and the other people's beliefs tell them to be traders, and others, scavengers.

A logical explanation for deviant behaviours or moral crimes is that a prostitute would earn much more than bank clerks at the end of the month. As earlier said, social environment is a factor that strongly influences behaviour. There is a symbiotic relationship between man and environment. Lack of information can be a serious internal barrier to action, because it is not always obvious to an individual how to act effectively on his or her attitudes. Religious, moral and ethical teachings and principles are used to encourage proper individual behaviours. For example, the ten commandments of the Judeo-Christian religious traditions proscribe certain behaviours (e.g. murder and adultery) and prescribe others (honouring one's

parents).¹⁷ This is a point that Sonia attempted to use helping Raskolnikoff onto the path of his regeneration.

Education can change attitudes and specific environmental beliefs, but it cannot quickly or easily change ethics or values. Furthermore, education is not likely to work if it promotes attitudes that clash with people's basic ethics and values. If an educator tells people that in order to have a clean environment they must sacrifice financial security, food or time with their families, people who value these things will reject the educator's method.¹⁸

SOME MANIFESTATIONS OF HUMAN INCLINATIONS IN CRIME AND PUNISHMENT

Obafemi Awolowo was influenced by Plato and Hegel. Plato said the soul is made up of the appetitive, the courageous and reason. This is the tripartite concept of the soul. The appetitive spirit governs the majority of the soul. That is the desire for food wealth and material things.

People who are governed by reason are those that have discovered the true state of being.

According to Awolowo, in his theory of 'Mental Magnitude', education is not about becoming a professional, nor about earning a meal ticket. It is speared towards the making of a total man. A total man is a person with a sound mind and a sound body. Every man has instincts, desires and emotions etc. If a man is governed by these things, he ceases to be a man but a beast. There is nothing wrong with taking care of the physical but these things should be checked and controlled.¹⁹ In essence, Raskolnikoff and especially Svidrigailoff are not total men because they are not governed by reason. They are lacking in focus.

Raskolnikoff as we see him has a split personality. He is a different person at different times. Raskolnikoff is said to hate the other 'Raskolnikoff' that erupts from some suppressed layer of his consciousness to contradict the natural image of himself.

Another instance of his schizophrenia is his indecisiveness about whether or not to commit the crime and the cold and calculating way he stands before Alena's door and pretends to be muttering to himself in order to prompt her to be relaxed enough to open the door.

Schizophrenia is not a single pathology; it is a group of disorders. They have several characteristics in common. The presence of hallucinations, delusions and disturbances in a number of areas of behaviour including thinking, emotional responses, sense of identity and the inclination or ability to initiate and carry out goal directed activity.²⁰

Individuals with schizoid personality disorder are reserved, socially withdrawn, reclusive loners, they prefer to work and play alone and appear to lack the ability to form warm, close social relationships. People with a schizotypal personality disorder have odd ways of thinking, communicating and behaving. They are much more handicapped on the average than people with a schizoid personality disorder. Although schizotypal personality disorder is not a prediction of future schizophrenia, it is found more frequently in features of schizophrenia patients.²¹

Schizophrenics suffer from delusions of all sorts. A delusion is a faulty thinking, a misrepresentation of reality that is clung to despite strong evidence to the contrary. The same can be said of Raskolnikoff's theory of inferior and superior men.²²

Repression is when a past event was so deeply traumatic that the memory of it becomes buried and the person has no recollection of what happened. This has been known to occur for instance in some particular unpleasant cases of child abuse, where the adult has no conscious recollection of the events, but is nonetheless powerfully influenced by it. The repressed unconscious, initiates the schizoid personality.

Raskolnikoff can be said to be suffering from a personality disorder. This can be observed from the description he is given in the novel.

He wondered at himself. Razoumikhin was one of his most intimate friends at the university, although it must be observed, Raskolnikoff had very few. He shunned everybody, went about with no one, and studiously kept aloof from all, and soon he became equally avoided – None loved him, as, besides being poor, he was extremely proud and reserved.

The psychological description of characters involves Dostoevsky in the intimate delineation of the subconscious. In dreams, the subconscious manifests itself and achieves a special prominence. As a result, 'dream' is indispensable. It is the dream in part which symbolically directs our attention to the meaning of the story. Telling us what is going on within his characters, focusing on the internal-especially in the criminal, the psychotic, the epileptic, the delirious, the hysterical, chaos and disorder.²³

Dreams play a great role in Crime and Punishment, as the fullest expressions of personality. Raskolnikoff underlines this in his reaction to the fearful dream of the mare beating. The ostensible subject of his dream has been an incident from childhood, but he is quick to seize its real meaning. "My God!" he cries, "can it really be, that I will take an ax and strike her on the head, smash her skull... that I would slip in the sticky warm blood... with the ax... my God can it be?"³⁴

Svidrigailoff's hallucination, dreams and suicide comprise one of Crime and Punishment's most powerful sequences. Dostoevsky in an attempt to show the relationship between Raskolnikoff and Svidrigailoff, seems to bring the dreams Svidrigailoff has on his last night into correspondence, if not wholly exact with those Raskolnikoff had earlier. Svidrigailoff's first dream is of a spring day on which he looks at the dead body of a girl who had apparently

killed herself because of the atrocity he had committed on her body. Raskolnikoff's first dream is of the mare beating, which in the furious shout of a frenzied peasant- "why don't you strike her with an ax?"- is linked with his killing of the money lender.

Svidrigailoff looks with apathetic curiosity at the body of the victim; Raskolnikoff reacts with furious aversion to the image of the victim-to-be. Svidrigailoff's second dream is of a little girl, in whose eyes, even as he tries to protect her, he sees a reflection of his rapacious lust; Raskolnikoff's dream of his futile attempt to kill again. Raskolnikoff is unable to act in his dream as he had in his conscious state. Svidrigailoff is unable to act in any other way. The dreams pointing perhaps to the essential nature of both men show the unbridgeable gulf between them.²⁵

Raskolnikoff has four dreams, three of which are described by the narrator, one that he himself describes and in which he does not appear symbolically. The first three dreams are tied together by the common denominator of violence, and each reflects light on the other and in turn, it is illuminated. As always, the dreams project backward, forward and inward.

Having already thought of the crime, Raskolnikoff is subconsciously warning himself not to commit it. He is Nikola, and the savage beating of the mare foreshadows his own ax murder of the money lender and her sister. He even uses the butt end of the ax to kill the old woman, as Nikola uses the blunt crowbar to kill the horse, thereby prolonging death, as if to spite himself with the recognition of the enormous will to live inherent in all life (and when he uses the sharp edge on Elizabeth, it is only because he is totally surprised by her appearance, reacts in panic). The mood of the men, their sheer recklessness, their gross corporality, their hysteria to beat and destroy... the determination of the horse not to die, this total scene of chaos symbolises the tone and quality of the murders. The boy fondles the horse and sees blood; Raskolnikoff will see blood, not only during the murder, but compulsively, he will

return to the venue of the crime to see if it is still there. The dream therefore, predicts the future.²⁶

In his third dream, Raskolnikoff relives the actual murder and the stranger who called him murderer is juxtaposed into the murder scene itself- what is crucial is that for the first time, Raskolnikoff can see himself commit the crime, in relatively undisguised fashion, without the mitigation afforded by symbolic representation. His victim only laughs at him as he strikes her again and again and he is unable to kill her in her dream. This is surely because Raskolnikoff cannot stand to see himself actually kill again. That is, he is emotionally unable to project the crime in full detail because he is different now. This then is the major clue to his regeneration. Dostoevsky most sublimely and profoundly exploited the literary and philosophical potential of dreams in Crime and Punishment.

A person's consciousness can also be detected through his thoughts and belief, which is the reason why Dostoevsky makes use of the interior monologue, and the stream of consciousness techniques in this novel.

Raskolnikoff believes in his theory of superior and inferior men, which ends up leading to his downfall. Svidrigailoff believes in satisfying all his desires. This also leads to his downfall. Peter Looshin believes in his economic theory, which makes some sets of people subservient to others. This leads him to public disgrace. Also Raskolnikoff argues within himself over such topics as; crime, and the reason why criminals are caught, the process of murder, he has the audacity to call a human being a louse etc.

All these go to show Raskolnikoff's consciousness in detail, while exposing us to the difference in individual capabilities and tendencies.

Even economic deprivation, such as that suffered by Raskolnikoff cannot be viewed as final responsibility; it is a contributing motivational factor, but it cannot explain nor replace his lack of moral commitment to humanity.

In addition, the most widely used method of preventing crime is through the threat of punishment. Imprisonment is supposed to be a form of retribution imposed on society for wrongdoing, a means of deterring potential criminals, and a way of preventing future crimes by the same offender. Much controversy, however, surrounds the question of whether punishment deters crime. Although many ex-convicts commit new crimes after their release from prison, the fear of improvement may still act as a general restraint upon the law-abiding.

NOTES

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- 2 'Criminals are made not born: the Myth and Reality of Human Behaviour' p.4.
- 3 'Criminals are made not born: the Myth and Reality of Human Behaviour' p.5.
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- 6 E. Ronald, Irwin Sarason and Barbra R. Sarason. Psychology. The Frontiers of Behaviour. (New York: Harper and Row Publishers, 1986) p.232
- 7 Peter Leikmann, Crime at Work (Englewood Cliffs: N.J. Prentice Hall 1973) pp.23-26
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- 11 Dostoevsky: The Major Fiction. P.58
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- 13 Beebe Maurice, The Three Motives of Raskolnikoff: A re-interpretation of Crime and Punishment (London: College Press xvii, 1955) pp. 151-152.
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- 21 Psychology. The Frontiers of Behaviour. p.518.
- 22 Psychology. The Frontiers of Behaviour. p.537.
- 23 The Subconscious in Gogol and Dostoevsky and Its Antecedents. p. 95.
- 24 Ronald Fanger, Dostoevsky and Romantic Realism: A Study of Dostoevsky in relation to Balzac, Dickens and Gogol. (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1965) p.220
- 25 Dostoevsky: The Major Fiction. p.82
- 26 The Subconscious in Gogol and Dostoevsky and Its Antecedents. p.116.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISORIENTATION: SOME SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL EXPLANATIONS

A person's orientation has to do with his particular interests, activities or aims. Disorientation can therefore be viewed as a possession of interest, aims and the performance of activities that are negative. Possible reasons for the development of a criminal consciousness are beyond a single discussion. They could be viewed from the philosophical, psychological and even spiritual stand points of the character in question. As had been earlier stated in this research, a person's consciousness is usually as a result of sociological conditioning as well as other relevant factors such as a psychological makeup and other environmental factors.

Changes in human behaviour are usually as a result of learning. The process is an adaptive one, in that: the changes in behaviour are the result of interaction with the environment. As conditions change, new behaviours are learned and old ones are eliminated.

Interaction with other people affects all aspects of human behaviour as human development depends on the influence of other people from infancy to old age. We learn from other people through instruction or by example. The important people in our lives shape our emotions, thoughts and personalities. Our perceptions, which we think of as private solitary events are affected by our interaction with others.¹

It is believed the cruel acts beget cruel attitudes. However, in the novel Crime and Punishment, Raskolnikoff is not surrounded by cruel people, so it cannot be said that the people around him influenced him; rather it can be deduced that he was influenced by his late predecessors. Since that is not a direct influence, it leads to other possible factors involved in the process of creating a criminal.

Differences in consciousness can be noticed through an individual's actions. For instance, the following questions could be asked. Why, though living in almost similar crushing conditions of poverty does Dounia (Raskolnikoff's) sister, remain a legally upright member of the society, while Sonia gives herself to prostitution? Raskolnikoff becomes a murderer, and unlike Razoumikhin does not continue his studentship? An argument of course could be raised, stating that the environmental and social circumstances surrounding these conflicting characters are different. Dounia has the loving support of a mother, while Sonia is saddled with a consumptive and emotionally erratic stepmother, a drunken father who even goes as far as stealing from her, and starving steps-siblings. Just as this argument has been raised, one could raise another. Why does Sonia not commit murder instead of prostitution? The answer to this question is very simple. Both Sonia and Raskolnikoff live in Saint Petersburg, the city with dingy dwellings and poverty stricken conditions. The difference between those two lies in their psychological framework or inner mind. Where Raskolnikoff could devise means, propound theories and develop ideas that would support his murdering an old pawn broker, Sonia would be a prostitute and hold onto her Bible never being capable of shedding human blood. Dounia on the other hand would cling to her mother's blossom and suffer on.

Sigmund Freud explains through psychology that the human mind consists of the conscious mind, which is seen as the surface, clearly visible and apparent to the individual, the preconscious mind which consists of thoughts, ideas and beliefs which might temporarily be forgotten but which could easily be retrieved when needed. Then there is the unconscious mind, which contains all kinds of disturbing and emotionally significant ideas and memories and exerts a powerful though unseen influence on the conscious and preconscious mind. The concerns of the unconscious mind are not normally accessible to consciousness. There is no point asking people about their deeper motivations and anxieties because they are lodged in the unconscious mind so the person will not be able to describe them and generally would not

even know about their existence. Relating this to the novel one would observe that Raskolnikoff had the murder in his conscious, preconscious as well as unconscious mind. This is apparent in the fact that he planned the murder consciously.

In his preconscious mind, a look at his theories and beliefs and thoughts would reveal his murderous tendencies. Dreams are often direct manifestations of a person's unconscious mind. Raskolnikoff's dreams have been examined earlier on in this essay and found to have a direct reference to his act of murder. The Russian sociological background has been found to contain enough conflict, suffering and social violence to condition an individual's mind towards violence. The media is a very effective source of information. It encompasses both audio and visual. For instance, violence is part of American society. Many prime-time television programs and regular films show shooting, beating, car crashes etc. Domestic violence appears to be common at social and economic levels, and child abuse and wife beating have only recently been defined as crimes. This cultural tolerance and even encouragement of violent behaviour is surely one reason why the United States has higher rates of crimes than other industrial societies do.

Taking a sketchy look at the Russian novel it would be observed that it deals with social issues and it has a large role to play in Russian society. It takes a central position where information is being examined. A look at the novel of a particular epoch will reveal the preoccupation of the time in question. Taking the 19th century as an example, Dimitri Furmanov in his novel Laspayev (1923) gives a sober record of a peasant guerilla operation under a leader whose role it was to direct the heroic mass. A week (1992) sketches in sharp and cruel detail a peasant revolt against communist rule. This should give us an overview of the social situation in Russia in the Nineteenth century.

Robert Lord says;

The fundamental truth is the man is willful, capricious, and wants to do as he pleases. All man wants, is an absolutely free choice, however dear that freedom may cost him and wherever it may lead him to. Man has always been and will always be like this. The modern man may even do something incredibly stupid and wicked simply in order to prove that he is still his own arbiter. At this point, the way is open to the theme of Crime and Punishment

This fundamental truth, added to one's individual psyche, and then social environmental influence, would create quite an impression.

Furthermore, society, according to sociology, not only controls our development, but also shapes our identity, our thoughts, and our emotions. The structure of society becomes the structure of our own consciousness. Society does not stop at the surface of our skins. Society penetrates us as much as it envelopes us. An examination of Raskolnikoff's role models will reveal that his orientation is negative.

"...further on my article, I remember insisting on the idea that all legislators and rulers of men commencing with the earliest, down to Lycurgus, Solon, Mahomet, Napoleon, etc. have one and all been criminals for whilst giving laws, they have naturally broken through older ones which had been faithfully observed by society and transmitted by its progenitors. These men most certainly never

hesitated to shed blood as soon as they saw the advantages of doing so. (Crime and Punishment p 180

To expatiate further on Raskolnikoff's level of innate dis-orientations, an examination of some of the figures mentioned above can be taken. Rising to the command of the French Revolutionary Armies, Napoleon seized political power as first consul in 1797 and proclaimed himself Emperor in 1804. By repeated victories over various European coalitions, he extended French rule over much of Europe. He was finally defeated in 1814 to 15. Solon C. 639 – C. 589 BC, an Athenian statesman, in 594BC, was granted absolute authority to remedy grave ills affecting Athens.

A serious economic crisis had forced many Athenians into debt. Many had been sold into foreign lands as slaves. The monopoly of the aristocracy excluded many well to do people from participating in government. To avoid revolution or tyranny, Solon cancelled all debts and forbade debt slavery. He made wealth in place of birth the criterion for public officers by establishing for income classes and accorded political rights to members of each of the top three classes on a graduated scale. Solon also passed sumptuary legislation and he modified the Athenian system of weights and measures perhaps causing inflation.

These men obviously make an impact on Raskolnikoff's thinking. This statement can be justified in that when Raskolnikoff is trying to figure out why he committed the murder, he makes mention of desire to become a 'Napoleon.'

“ I was ambitious to become a Napoleon; that was why I committed the murder. The fact is that one day I asked myself the following question supposing Napoleon to have been in my place. Supposing that to advance his career had neither Toulon nor Egypt nor the crossing of Mont Blanc, but in lieu of all these brilliant exploits he

was on the point of committing a murder with a view to secure his future, would he have recoiled at the act of killing an old woman and robbing her of 3000 rubles? Would he have agreed that such a deed was too much wanting in prestige and much too a criminal one? I finally came to the conclusion that he not only would have, but that he would not have understood the possibility of such a thing. Every other expedient being out of his reach he would not have flinched, he would have done so without the smallest scruple.” Crime and Punishment p. 304

A look at Raskolnikoff’s philosophy as extracted from his article in the novel confirms the idea that Raskolnikoff’s criminal act was triggered by disorientation. As innocent as it might seem, Donia was willing to sacrifice herself to Looshin for her brother. In order to secure her brother's finances, she was willing to marry a man she did not love, and to fulfil all her marital obligations including sexual intercourse. This makes her only a little different from Sonia who is a prostitute in the real sense of the word. Sonia would continue to give herself to several men, while Donia would spend her life giving herself to a man she does not love. One could argue it out that Donia would be legally married to Peter Looshin so she would not be doing anything wrong while another could argue otherwise. Even the question of whether prostitution is a crime or not arises. Also the question about whether a crime is considered a crime in some communities also arises. What is considered illegal in one jurisdiction could be considered a mere fault in another so while Sonia is being viewed as a prostitute and is been referred to as a criminal in one jurisdiction, in another jurisdiction she could be viewed as someone who just broke a social norm.

PUNISHMENT AS A PREVENTIVE MEASURE

As earlier stated in this work, punishment is employed in some cases in order to prevent a repeat of the criminal offence in question. It also serves as a warning to others who may want to commit criminal acts. There are other different reasons why punishment is applied to offenders. In some cases, it is done to keep the criminal off the streets while in some cases it is applied in order to stimulate positive changes in the individual. Punishment comes in different forms; imprisonment with hard labour, or exile, death by hanging, electrocution or firing squad.

Punishment or lack of it plays a major part in either encouraging or discouraging disorientation. In a country where people commit heinous crimes and get away with them, a person who resides in such a country grows up harbouring the thought that he could commit a crime and go unpunished. A novel that represents a crime without punishment situation properly is an American Dream by Norman Mailer. Its frantic action consists of a great deal of sexual exertion and it is centred on a homicide.

The protagonist's killing of his wife, a wealthy heiress during a tussle in which hard words and harder blows are exchanged. It is true enough that the murderer was unpremeditated but neither can it be said that this act of ultimate violence committed by Stephen Rojack, the protagonist, is merely an accident and he commits it with enormous exhilaration. Already on page eight before the episode of the killing is introduced, Rojack acknowledges that he had long known that there was murder within him, and he speculates that the exhilaration accompanying it must come from possessing such strength. I was weary with the most honourable fatigue and my flesh seemed new [after the homicide] I had not felt so nice since I was twelve and immediately after observing this, Rojack rushes to the maids room to

*engage her in sex acts both plain and fancy. It is not that he had been having an affair with her, killing excites him sexually.*⁶

In this novel the homicide not only goes unpunished, (crime without punishment), but it is also without any kind of consequence either public or private. Viewing a case like this, one could conclude that there is unlimited freedom in such a society, so there is ample opportunity for criminal consciousness to develop to other proportions. However, the threat of punishment prevents mass crime in societies. It goes a long way in fostering social control. Different punishments have their different levels of efficacy for instance, it may not be actually legal for a minister to seduce his organist, but the threat of being banned forever from the exercise of his profession will be a much more effective control over this temptation than the possible threats of going to jail.⁷

Ridicule and gossip are potent instruments of social control in primary groups of all sorts. Many societies use ridicule as one of the main controls over children. The child conforms not for fear of punishment, but in order not to be laughed at.⁸ This however, applies to adults in some cases. Unfortunately, criminals rarely think much of people's opinion of them. One of the most devastating means of punishment at the disposal of a human community is to subject one of its members to systemic opprobrium and ostracism. An example of this would be shunning among the Amish Mennonites. An individual who breaks one of the principal taboos of the group for example, by getting sexually involved with an outsider is shunned. This means that while permitted to continue to work and live in the community, not a single person will ever speak to him ever. It is hard to imagine a more cruel punishment. Capital punishment, the most controversial of all these forms of punishment, is seen as a paradigm of bad faith. Examples of bad faith can be seen in the prosecution of homosexual, racial

prejudice or discrimination. In other communities, it is viewed as the most effective method of punishment especially for serial killers and other hardened criminals.

Raskolnikoff is not given commensurate punishment for his crime. This is basically because; he does not show any genuine signs of contrition after committing his crime. He is convinced that he has a right to kill. Edward Wasiolek goes as far as saying that Raskolnikoff commits the crime to prove his superiority; he pursues his punishment and suffering to protect the superiority. Even more, he commits the crime in order to fail.

Even during a discussion with Donia, Raskolnikoff exclaims that;

*'My crime? What crime say you? he retorted in a sudden fit of frenzy.
Is it a crime to have killed some vile and noisome vermin, an old
usurer that was obnoxious to all, a vampire living on the life of the
poor? Why, murders of that kind ought to make up for many a crime, I
do not even give it a thought as to atonement bah! Why should
everyone hiss out to me the word, "crime, crime!" Now that I am
determined of my own free will to face dishonor, the absurdity to such
a resolution strikes me more than ever; it is only weakness and
puerility that is leading me to take that step, unless it may be self
interest, as Porphyus counseled. Crime and Punishment p.379*

Dounia asked him how he could talk like that when he was guilty of shedding human blood and he replied,

“Suppose I am. And does not everybody do so? Has it not always flowed in streams down here below? Do not men, who have spilt it like water, immediately ascend the capital where they are hailed as saviours of their kind? Look into things before you judge. I also wished to benefit my kind for hundreds, thousands of sensible deeds would amply have made up for this mad freak or rather blunder; for my original purpose was not so mad as one may think; though often for want of skill, the brightest schemes look hollow. I only want to make myself an independent person, to assure my entrance into life, to find the means for then success would have been certain. But I have failed and am a villain! Had I but carried my point the victor's wreath would have been mine; whilst now I am only good for the dogs! Crime and Punishment pp. 379-380

By reading this statement it would be obvious to the reader that the crime was premeditated. He tells Dounia that the landlady's daughter [the girl he had loved] that he had more than once talked with her about this plan but with her alone. He said ‘I trusted her with a project which was destined to have such a lamentable ending’.

All these are followed up by the fact that all the jury asserted that Raskolnikoff was suffering from monomania and temporary insanity; he refused to take up that line of defence. He took full responsibility for his crimes. Such a person should not be left to roam free, even after eight years in Siberia for he could propound another theory that justifies mass murder, and could carry it out causing a lot of innocent people to lose their lives.

Though it could be raised that punishment is not always appropriate for sometimes the wrong person could be punished. This is one of the major reasons why capital punishment is widely discouraged. Nevertheless, in a lot of cases this is the kind of punishment that is usually given out especially to people who have committed manslaughter.

NOTES

¹ Neil. R. Carlson, Psychology. The Science of Behaviour. (London: Allyn and Bacon Inc, 1987). p. 527

² Marvin Wolfgang and Franco Ferracutti, The Subculture of Violence. (London: Tavistock, 1967). p.140

³ Robert Lord, Dostoevsky's Essays and Perspectives. (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1970). P. 42

⁴ B. Ben Jones, Napoleon: Man and Myth. (London: Hodder and Soughton, 1977). p.122.

⁵ Philip Rahv, Essays on Literature and Politics 1932-1972. (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1978). p. 99

⁶ Peter L Berger, Invitation to Sociology. A Humanistic Perspective. (USA: Doubleday and Co, 1963). p.86

⁷ Invitation to Sociology. A Humanistic Perspective. p.88

⁸ Invitation to Sociology. A Humanistic Perspective. P. 99

CONCLUSION

Criminal behaviour or negative social behaviour cannot be avoided or prevented entirely. This is because of the involvement of a psychological factor in the evolution of criminal behaviour. Psychologically, it has been explained in Freud's theory of social behaviour that;

Social behaviour is motivated by basic biological drives (the Id), specialized experiences, (the super-ego), and the intellectual capacity (the ego) the demand of the Id for physical gratification is curbed by the super ego, which acts as instruments of social control and by the ego which represents the ability to make rational judgement. If early childhood socialization does not proceed formally, the theory goes, the super ego will be defective and the individual will not develop conventional moral standards. If the super-ego fails to develop at all, the result is a psychopathic personality or a completely amoral person.¹

Personality disorders which stem from internal disorders, also cause criminal acts to be carried out. Unfortunately it is not possible to prevent people from having personality disorders. It is only possible for them to go through intensive therapy. In severe cases, they could be kept away from normal human environments, lest they wreck irreparable damage to persons and property. To a large extent, the novel Crime and Punishment was able to accomplish what it set out to accomplish. It presented a situation where an interest in nihilism and individualism resulted in an act of unpardonable social deviance.

Dostoevsky evidently intended for Raskolnikoff to represent a type of trend. He was one of the 'new men'. The 'new men' is a phenomenon that is common to Russian literature. It

treats the appearance of men who have emerged with new ideas and new modes of life and ways of reasoning. The writer succeeded in achieving his aim by using the stream of consciousness technique, the interior monologue, the vivid sketches, etc. All these techniques delve into the psychological character of a person in question, his private musings, thoughts, ideas, etc. and unearth them.

Dostoevsky has been able to reveal the link between economic conditions, negative inclinations, and crime. In some cases a person has no money and no means of livelihood and his situation forces him into committing a crime. In addition to his innate negative inclination, Raskolnikoff is forced into committing a crime. This is partly Raskolnikoff's reason for committing the crime for he gives economic constraints as one of his reasons in the novel.

In another case, a man has a lot of money and everything else he wants but by giving himself up to hedonistic pleasures, he turns himself into a cold-blooded criminal. Therefore, one cannot generalise by saying a criminal is made as a result of his consciousness alone or his consciousness merged with environmental and social factors, or mental states. A perfect composition cannot be made. Often, it is as a result of a network of reasons that a crime is committed and every criminal has his own peculiar composition, just as every serial killer has his own peculiar pattern of murder or homicide.

However there is still that fundamental reason which sometimes makes it impossible for punishment to redeem criminals from their benighted chasm. Punishment alone oftentimes cannot effectively dispel those negative seeds, which lurk within a person and form what is known as a criminal consciousness.

NOTES

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p. 513.

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